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Moving a Nursing Examination from Dichotomous to Polytomous CAT

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Scope of Project

- Extant Literature and Practice Analysis showed significant increase in the need for clinical judgment (CJ) skills in entry-level nurses
- NCLEX measured CJ but not in a systematic manner
- GOAL: evaluate and assess CJ on an expanded NCLEX exam, aka Next Generation NCLEX
- Issues:
 - New items were composed of very different item presentations and response types
 - Leveraging research & calibration results from non-optimal circumstances

Overview

- Numerous approaches were taken across 16+ designed pools for research and calibrations over 5 years.
 - Numerous research designs and calibration designs were used to address outstanding issues
- Today, we'll highlight some methods employed
 - Pre-launch:
 - Evaluate effects of recalibrating extant, legacy items from dichotomous to polytomous
 - Evaluate new CJ items and sets along with initial calibration results
 - Post-launch
 - Validity evidence: Seeding legacy and new items into pre-test pools to evaluate the drift and misfit

Recalibration of Extant/Legacy Items

- Recalibrated all MR items using the PCM
 - Data used:
 - Historical pre-test responses
 - Pre-test pools in contemporaneous pools
 - Validate and evaluate stability of thresholds:
 - Randomly selected recalibrated items for post-launch pre-test pools
 - Evaluated drift and misfit between calibrations

Recalibration Results – Pre-launch

- Operational MR items scored dichotomously → polytomous

Exam	MR items selected for recalibration	Items failed the statistical criteria	% of items that passed to remain operational
RN	1,855	49	97%
PN	1,185	43	96%

- Minimal loss of items moving to polytomous
- Difficult MR items → good polytomous items covering greater width of ability

Recalibration Results – Post-launch

- Misfit & Drift of items from OP exams (April 2023 and beyond)

Exam	MR items in OP exam	Items flagged for misfit OR drift	Percent
RN	859	7	< 1%
PN	609	0	0 %

- Minimal items showing either misfit or drift

Calibrating CJ Items and Sets

- In addition, new item development was needed
- However, new items were dramatically different from extant, legacy items
 - Unlike the recalibrated extant items,
 - These items would stick out in a pre-test pool
 - These items would be known to be non-scored, research items
 - Using them in the pretest pool was considered too risky
 1. Candidates could either spend too much or too little time, as NCLEX is a timed exam, which could negatively affect their focus on the core exam
 2. The pre-test pool was configured to select single items; so, there would have been a large amount of work to adapt and, thus, limiting our opportunity to test out items

Calibrating CJ Items and Sets

- Solution: add a section after the scored CAT, the Special Research Section (SRS)
 - Allowed candidates to finish their exams without any concern
 - Opt-in to the SRS if they chose and spend as much time evaluating the new item types and sets (within the max time of the exam)
- Problems:
 - As the exam was finished, candidates knew that the SRS had all unscored items
 - Candidates could skip all items or might respond haphazardly given no stakes were associated with the items
- How to use these responses for research and calibration?

Dealing with Unengaged Candidates

- Problem:
 - Identify engaged candidates from unengaged for research and calibration purposes
- Solution:
 - Utilize multiple methods for determining motivated candidates and compare results
- Methods employed:
 - Item level solution: Wise's approach to identifying engagement (note, this is only 1 of a few we used)
 - Response times $\geq 10\%$ of the mean response time on that item (min of 10 sec), and those items represented $> 50\%$ of item responses on the form (RTE: Response Time Effort)
 - Candidate results were used but items not meeting the $\geq 10\%$ threshold were recoded as skipped
 - Form level solution: conservative criteria
 - Answer all questions on form and spend more than 30 sec on each item (~ 1.5 sd's below the average response time)

Comparing Calibration Methods

- Issue: SRS were forms based but operational CAT is not
 - When operational, new CJ items would need to be calibrated using person anchors → would they be stable?
- Calibration methods:
 - Item anchoring for concurrent calibration
 - Person anchoring
 - Compare results

Basic Research Design

- Compared calibration results:
 - Person vs item anchor
 - Person vs form level 'motivated' responders
- Would like $a \sim b \sim c \sim d$

Calibration Anchor	Completer Method	
	<i>Item</i>	<i>Form</i>
<i>Person</i>	a	b
<i>Item</i>	c	d

Basic Set-up of the SRS

- Every SRS had multiple research designs embedded for gathering validity evidence
 - For this, we'll just discuss the use of the forms for calibration
- Used linear forms and randomization selection
- Form construction:
 - Utilized anchor items from extant bank
 - Spiraled new items and item sets across forms
 - Cloned each forms to make 3 equivalent forms: item sets rotated in beginning, middle, and end of form

Results

	<u>SS</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>PR(>F)</u>
Completer	0.001	1	0.001	0.969
Anchor	17.541	1	18.855	0.000
Interaction	0.002	1	0.002	0.963
Residual	870.756	936		

Multiple Comparison of Means - Tukey HSD, FWER=0.05

<i>Group 1</i>	<i>Group 2</i>	<i>MeanDiff</i>	<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>
item	Person	0.2732	0.15	0.397

- No differences between the completer methods
- Moderate differences (Cohen's $d = 0.28$) between calibration methods
- Correlations between median threshold across all 4 conditions ≥ 0.99

Scatterplot Threshold Values

Correlations	item_item	form_person	item_person
form_item	0.99	0.98	0.98
item_item		0.98	0.98
form_person			0.99

Post-launch Misfit & Drift of CJ Items

Exam	CJ in OP exam	CJ flagged for misfit OR drift	Percent
RN	2,169	139	6.5%
PN	1,796	85	4.7%

- Reseeded the SRS CJ item and sets back into the EXP pools to compare SRS calibrations with live-exam results
- Only 4-7% of items showed misfit or drift (using person anchor method)

Overall Results

- Extant items:
 - Pre-launch: Recalibrating extant dichotomous items to polytomous model did not result in many items lost.
 - Post-launch: Polytomous calibrations almost no misfit or drift.
- New CJ items in SRS:
 - Pre-launch:
 - Item- and form-level methods for controlling analysis to engaged candidates appeared to coincide.
 - Moderate differences in calibration methods found.
 - Post-launch: Drift and misfit were minimal when compared to SRS calibrations.

Questions??